

SEO TECHNIQUES AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN DIGITAL MARKETING

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Introduction

We are the generation that has been watching the multi-dimensional growth of business since barter. Now-a-day’s e-Business plays a vital role in transforming goods and services. Everything from essentials to luxury items are available in online market. The growth of e-commerce has grown exponentially, from where we were, to what we and our dependents can add to anything. The growth of e-commerce is unstoppable due to lack of customer time, increasing traffic congestion and the next phase of money transfer. Today, the e-commerce market is seen as a completely open market with no barriers of its own. In this market, anyone with the marketing ability to seduce a customer is the king here. In such an e-commerce business, it is necessary to know the rules that are the basics for success as an individual and as a company.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing can be termed as the efforts used to promote that using electronic device with the help of internet. Digital platforms such as search engines, social media, email and various websites which are used to connect current and future customers for the promotion of the business. Search engine ranking is very important for successful digital marketing. In digital marketing most of the energy is spent for getting higher rank in search engine.

Importance of Digital Marketing

As far as Digital marketing is concerned, buyers do not have to create a market. The Digital marketing marketplace has simplified the job of bringing both non-marketable and marketable products to buyers. The biggest problem that buyers face in the traditional marketing business system is the supply chain. That is, the additional costs added to the product from the manufacturer to the consumer increases the cost of the manufactured goods and services. But, the manufacturer may also be the seller in the Digital marketing market or the manufacturer may be the seller in the e-marketplace where the customer can meet them directly. As a result, costs are reduced and market opportunities are created. This, in turn, will create buyers. Therefore, individual buyers in the Digital marketing are not the only market creators. Conversely, any goods or services that have a return on investment will create a business opportunity.

Digital marketing is not about increasing the number of visitors to a website or increasing the status of the web by increasing the Website Traffic through its related advertisements, rather, it's about keeping visitors and customers on a website, engaging them in business transactions and, consequently, keeping them coming back to the website and retaining them.

In most cases, the advantage of Digital marketing as seen in traditional business is, that you can know the return for every penny you spend on advertising. Therefore, in Digital marketing, for audience growth it is essential to act on the basis of how you can build customers and retain

customers rather than what you spend. This will help you to establish yourself as a profitable person in the open market.

No matter what is the business model, it is important to maintain the best possible relationship with your customers. But, particularly in Digital marketing, it is even more important because, the sellers and buyers often do not meet at e-commerce. Therefore, in a business that takes place without meeting each other, it is not normal to understand each other's feelings and ideas and strengthen the business relationship. It is also the hub of most Digital marketing. The reason is that most e-businesses are being pushed out of the competitive market as a result of their failure to strengthen pre-service and post Customer service relationships.No matter how big the company grows in the market, it is essential to have the customer relationship at the highest level. Otherwise, it will become a factor that will end your business.

Why SEO techniques?

Many web users consider search results that appear on the first page when searching in search engines to be their correct search results. The links that appear first on the first page are the ones that are most sought after by the searchers and find the ones that are relevant to them on the website of those links. Those who do so are likely to become buyers. Buyers doing so are more likely to become repeated buyers. So companies involved in the digital business are pushing for their webpages to appear first in the search results. Businesses adopt various Search Engine Optimization techniques for this.

What are the SEO Techniques?

"Page Rank" are assigned by Google to web pages based on their perceived authority. This authority comes from links that redirects to those pages, from other pages that have public relations. In Simply words, the higher the number of PR links, the higher the number of PR page will become.The work done to increase search engine rankings is consistent with organic or natural results. You can pay for the chance to appear more in search engine results through Google Advertising campaigns like Google AdWords. SEO techniques can be divided into two types namely on page SEO and Off page SEO.Some of the SEO tactics are given below in this [Figure](#).

On-Page SEO

On-Page SEO is nothing but Onsite SEO. It helps to show the content to users when searching in Search Engine. It includes contents, Title tags and internal links and URL of that page. When a web page contains same keywords in Title, Subtitle and body of the text page then the search

engine will take this as the subject of the page and will be started to index that keyword. When the keyword repeats in so many places of that page, then the search engine will give more importance. Using targeted keyword into the first 100 words of the content or articles is an important one to show the content as more relevant to the search keyword. Keyword frequency also helps the search engine to identify the relevant content.

Title tags

Title tags which are also called ~~known~~ as title elements, are equally ~~just as~~ important as Meta descriptions so as to attract user engagement. Search engine results page will display title tags to users with a Meta description. Title tags play an important role in improving SEO results and social sharing capabilities. The title tag should be a concise and accurate description of the content of the page. Under no circumstances should it deliberately mislead the user. Typically, title tags appear in three main places: SERPs, browsers, and external websites. Title Tag Modifying words such as best, guide, how to fast, review also help to increase the search engine ranking.

Meta description

A short description of a webpage that gives you a small description of a page which appears in the Search engine results page, so it plays a great role in maximizing your chances because you wrote that the search engine will check it first and, as a result, people will read it first and then Will click and visit your website.

Content

Crisp writing will engage and encourage the customers to read more about our product features and details. Images, Screenshots, gif animations will attract the viewers. Creating a tree chart site map of the pages ie URL will help to search engine and also to the viewers to navigate to the most relevant content. It will help to see more pages of a websites and to help more products also. Updating details often and regularly is very important one to a growing marketer.

Keyword

Keywords are the words ~~or and~~ phrases that the searchers enter in search engines, which are also known as "search queries". Content developer will give some keywords on their pages that ~~to be~~ relevant to what people are looking for, so they have a better chance of finding your content in the results.

User engagement

Google and other search engines want to provide meaningful results to users. So, they try to reward the content they click and interact with. If a website does not provide relevant information to users and users do not find users worthy of their involvement, SERP ranking will be dropped and the site will be replaced with one that is considered highly relevant.

Page Speed

Overload of page components may increase the page loading time. A page which takes more time to open will be rejected / skipped by the content searcher. So many Page loading speed analytic tools are available. By analysing necessary action can be taken to reduce the page loading time. It is better to avoid flash objects and also Images may be compressed.

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Rich Snippet

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சூடான-சுவையான அறிவியல் விவாத ஆய்வுக்கட்டுரைகள்.

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Alt tag for objects

Adding meta data description to the objects such as video, images, pdf, audio and other media files will help to index that item in search engines. To get more CTR it is very important to give effective Meta description to the hosted/uploaded objects/files.

URL with keyword

An URL is commonly referred to as a "web address", refers to the location of a resource (such as a webpage) on the Internet. Even if the title of this page is hidden, URL will give the people and search engine a clear idea of what is the content given in this particular page.

Internal outbound links

Linking to the other page of a website is called internal link. The outbound links is the number of links added to a post or page. Links from other websites is called incoming links or backlinks. Links to another website called Outgoing links. It may be no followed and followed links. Search engine will not follow "No Followed" links. Search engines can follow "followed links", add value to the article, and perhaps rank it higher. Related External page link also helps the search engine to identify the content. If the URL of a web page reflects the content it ~~will get~~ will get more effect to the search engine ranking.

Off-Page SEO

"Off-Page SEO" refers to all the activities that are carried out away from the website to raise the ranking of a page with search engines. Off-page SEO involves the actions of a website in an effort to increase the site's search engine rankings. Common off-page SEO practices include creating backlinks, promoting branded searches, and increasing engagement and participation on social media.

NAP Citations

The abbreviation "NAP" stands for name, address and phone number. This is an important factor in the local SEO and the impact that Google and other search engines have on local purpose searches.

People often cite instances of NAP data on the web. A quote when your NAP data is displayed on directory sites such as Yelp or Angie's List, newspaper articles, blog posts, etc.

Reviews

Getting High quality reviews and comments will attract the customer and search engine also. Nowadays most of the digital buyers before buying commodities throw online mode they read the reviews of the product given by the previous buyers. If a Commodity got more good opinion/ review rank the possibility of purchase will be very high.

Guest Posting

Guest Post is the writing and publishing of an article by a third party on someone else's website or blog. When creating /writing guest post, digital marketing website will be included in suitable places. By this way digital marketing firms website get more link. Small Scale digital marketing firms are writing answers in the Answers websites such as Quora.com, yahoo answers, wiki answers, etc.,

Link from trusted sites

Getting Links from trusted websites such as government sites, educational sites and non-profit organizations and other Reliable sites, are difficult to obtain, because they are generally reluctant to link with high-level bureaucracy, high standards or businesses. However, links from such sites can be valuable.

Press release

News release submission refers to writing about a company's new events, products or services and submitting them to PR sites. It will help to popularize an e-commerce business event, products or services on the web and to improve digital marketer page's SEO. A news release should have keywords that are optimistic, truthful and informative so that, it will keep readers interested. Also, it should be used to share news content with target users.

Conclusion

Digital Marketing is mostly based on Digital Marketer's Website available when searching in Search Engine. By designing a digital marketing website attractive and proper designing and using effective SEO approaches, a digital marketer can succeed in the market. By Using the Effective on-page SEO and Off-Page SEO a website can get a higher rank in search engine's search results. One who has designed effective SEO friendly website may not spend much amount for Advertisement and also can reduce the mediator's commission. So the end user can be benefited more.

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